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**COMPARISON OF RAPID DIAGNOSTIC TEST AND MICROSCOPY TESTING OF
MALARIA PARASITES AMONG PREGNANT WOMEN AND CHILDREN
ATTENDING ANTENATAL CARE IN AGUDAMA HEALTH FACILITY IN
YENAGOA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, BAYELSA STATE, NIGERIA**

David Nnemakpanheme Samuel Chezue¹ & Joan Gbonhinbor²

¹Department of Animal and Environmental Biology,
University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria,

²Department of Science Laboratory Technology,
Federal Polytechnic, Ekowe, Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

Abstract

The effectiveness of the Rapid Diagnostic Test (RDT) Kit was compared with that of microscopy for the evaluation of malaria infection in children and pregnant women in a health facility in Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The study determined the prevalence of malaria in children and pregnant women; compared the sensitivity and specificity in children and the sensitivity and specificity in pregnant women attending health facilities in Yenagoa in Bayelsa State. A total of 191 patients (40 children and 151 pregnant women) were sampled for this purpose. The prevalence of infection observed for microscopy was 29(67.5%) in children and 24(15.9%) in pregnant women while RDT showed 5(12.5%) for children and 15(9.9%) for pregnant women. The evaluation of RDT showed low specificity of 11.1% but a high level of specificity of 25.0% for microscopy. This study showed that RDT was not sensitive as microscopy in the detection of malaria infection in the study area. Ministry of health and all families should ensure that contact with a mosquito bite is avoided to reduce the spread of malaria disease to pregnant women and children in the study area.